

SOME CHALLENGES IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This article suggests some difficulties in teaching English in the EFL classroom. Being a great EFL teacher is not only to teach, but also to inspire and empower learners and the main goal is to excite the them about learning, speaking, reading, writing, and comprehending English.

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The English is the world language now and teaching can be difficult but what's even more troublesome is being responsible for keeping students awake and interested. This is the task of an EFL teacher first and foremost.

1. *Teacher centered sessions or learners are dependent on the teacher.* A lot of learners always automatically look to the teacher for correct answers instead of trying themselves. If the teacher encourages them to answer each time, it can become a prejudicial problem. Teacher should focus on giving positive encouragement. It helps to get students more comfortable and more willing to answer even incorrectly.

2. *Using a native language categorically during the sessions.* It is the most common problem in teaching English as a foreign language. As an EFL teacher, it's important to encourage students to use English, and only English. However, if students begin talking in their native language, a teacher has to move closer and ask them direct questions like "Have you got a question?" Another idea is to establish a set of ground rules in the classroom and develop a penalty system for when they use their first language. For example: if someone is caught using their native language three times, have them recite a poem in front of the class as a fine (in English). It ought to be remembered, for the 1-2 hours they are in English class, it must be English only.

3. *A learner is absent-minded, noisy or disobedient.* This can happen, no matter what, in every classroom. If the entire class is acting up, it may be the fault of the teacher, i.e. boring material or poor classroom management. If it is one particular learner, an instructor should react swiftly to show dominance. In order to resolve the issue, an EFL teacher must be strict and institute discipline if needed. If it continues to happen, further disciplinary action through the school's director could be pursued.

4. *The lesson doesn't go where a teacher would like it to.* When teaching English as a foreign language, a moderator can always count on students hijacking a lesson. To some extent, it can be a good thing. It shows that learners' interest, and as long as they are participating and conversating in English, it is a productive experience. However, if the lesson goes too far off topic, in a direction an instructor doesn't want it to go, it's important to correct the problem by diverting the conversation.

5. *Personalities friction.* Not everyone in an EFL classroom will become the best of friends. If drama arises between certain students, the easiest solution is to separate them from one another. If the tension persists, switching a student to another classroom may be the teacher's only option.

6. *Students hesitate what to do, or do the wrong thing.* This often occurs when teaching English as a foreign language. In fact, it's often the fault of the teacher. If the instructions to an assignment yield look of confusion and soft whispers among students, there is a solution. In order to avoid this problem, it's important to make sure if the instruction is clear. Speaking clearly and strongly, gestures, mime, and short concise sentences could be used. Models and examples of the activity must be used importantly.

7. *Students are bored, inattentive, or unmotivated.* It is often the teacher's fault that class is boring. Fortunately, with proper planning, this problem can be solved. An interesting theme can be chosen to the lesson; one that the students can relate to and one a teacher knows they will enjoy. It will automatically give them some motivation and interest. An instructor is always to get to know about the learners and identify their interests and needs and then design his sessions accordingly.

8. *Strong student dominance.* An EFL teacher should always takes into consideration learners with different abilities and language skills. While it is good to have some students who excel in the classroom, it is important that they don't take away from others. If any students begin to constantly "steal the show," take care. Focus on calling on weaker students in the class to answer questions. They have to be encouraged, but gently deflected some answers from the strong students and given production time to other not-so-strong members of the class.

9. *Students are unprepared.* The last thing which an EFL teacher dislikes for learners to drop out simply because they felt lost when they are unprepared and makes sure learners are all on the same page before moving onto a new topic by concept checking multiple times, and encouraging individual participation.

Teaching and learning are the two sides of a coin. Learning is a progressive process from the cradle to the tomb. A well-chosen method plays a significant role in teaching and learning process. Drawing attention to the interactive methods rises the value of teaching effectively.

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